

Peak Sanctuary of Petsofas

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Entry tags: Aegean, Minoan Religions, Religious Group, Religious Place

Situated in the far east of Crete, the hill of Petsofas rises just south of the ancient settlement of Palaikastro (also known as Roussolakos). In the Bronze Age, a religious sanctuary sat atop its 270 m summit, one of many so-called "peak sanctuaries" uncovered at elevated peaks across Crete. Petsofas, however, was the first of this shrine type to be noted and investigated, its large quantities of ceramic figurines suggestive of a particular Minoan ritual practice.

Date Range: 2000 BCE - 1500 BCE

Region: Peak Sanctuary of Petsofas

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Greece, Crete

The Bronze Age peak-top sanctuary of Petsofas, Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Myres, J.L. 1902/1903. "Excavations at Palaikastro II: The Sanctuary-Site of Petsofa." *BSA* 9: 356-387.

– Source 2: Rutkowski, Bogdan. 1991. *Petsophas: A Cretan Peak Sanctuary*. Studies and Monographs in Mediterranean Archaeology and Civilization 1. Warsaw: Art and Archaeology.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Petsofas caught the attention of archaeologists when a local shepherd girl found a number of small ceramic animal figurines close to the stones of a terrace wall extending across the face of the hill (Myres 1902/1903, 357). In the summer of 1903, John L. Myres began small excavations at the top of the hill to investigate further and uncovered hundreds of fragmented and intact figurines, both human and animal, as well as pottery sherds scattered amongst low walls. When Myres was required to return to Oxford later in the season, Charles T. Currelly took over excavations and finished out the year (Bosanquet et al. 1902/1903, 276). Many decades later, Bogdan Rutkowski revisited the Petsofas material excavated by the British School at Athens projects and published his restudy in a 1991 volume.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1903

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: British School at Athens Excavations at Palaikastro - "The Second Campaign - Outlying Sites"

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: A small 270 m peak beyond the village of Palaikastro in East Crete and south of the archaeological site known as Roussolakkos.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Type of feature

– Terracing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The site itself is purposely situated away from the urbanized area, at the top of a rural peak, but the settlement of Palaikastro (also known as Roussolakkos) is not far from the sanctuary, just north and slightly west of the peak.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Bronze Age settlement of Palaikastro (also known as Roussolakkos) is not far from the sanctuary, situated at the foot of Petsofas' northern slope.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The Bronze Age settlement of Palaikastro (also known as Roussolakkos) is not far from the sanctuary, situated at the foot of Petsofas' northern slope. The sanctuary is accessible by foot from the settlement (approximately a 45-60 minute walk from the settlement to the peak sanctuary).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The remains of walls were excavated by John Myres (1902-3, 357-360) atop the peak in the early 20th century. Terracotta figurines were found throughout these spaces, and at least one yielded a plaster floor and plastered bench (Myres 1902-3, plate VII), though Rutkowski (1991, 20) attributes these features to a later Neopalatial addition at the sanctuary; the earlier terrace walls would have created open-air ritual areas used in the early Middle Minoan period (Rutkowski 1991, 17). In MM III/LM I or LM I, a rebuilding took place and a new two-room shrine was created adjacent to the terraces (Rutkowski 1991, 20). It is unclear whether or not these rooms were both enclosed, but their cultic nature seems certain based on the deposits of figurines found within them.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: There are two main phases of construction: MM I (terrace walls and open-air areas) and MM III/LM I (terrace walls, open-air areas, and cultic rooms which may or may not have been enclosed).

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Although this grouping of walls and spaces is the main construction atop the Petsofas peak sanctuary, votive figurines were found across the peak, amongst rocks and crevices. Indeed, Rutkowski (1991, 21) notes that the many objects and large number of stones found south-east of the shrine building perhaps suggest that another structure once stood on this part of the peak. Furthermore, the many ceramic sherds and figurines uncovered on a peak beside the sanctuary, just 80 m away from the excavated building, are perhaps indicative of another ritual area belonging to the sanctuary.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Notes: The structure/spaces were presumably used to facilitate ritual activities performed at the peak sanctuary, but the exact nature of such activities are unknown. The small-scale objects (including terracotta figurines and miniature ceramic vessels) deposited at Petsofas and atop other similar peak sanctuaries are often interpreted as votive offerings (Myres 1902-03, 358). The anthropomorphic figurines are often believed to represent adorants (Pilali Papasteriou 1992, 208), the ceramic limbs such as arms or feet to be physical manifestations of prayers for healing (Myres 1902-3; Rutkowski 1991), and miniature ceramic vessels as offerings to ensure a bountiful crop and fertility (Marinatos 1986, 71; Watrous 1995, 401; Chryssoulaki 2001, 62; Kyriakidis 2005, 161).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: It is assumed that peak sanctuaries were places of worship, with ritual activities involving the dedication of votive offerings and pouring of libations, as well as possible feasts, drinking rituals, and sacrifices. These activities appear to have been directed at supernatural beings or deities, though the lack of textual evidence makes it difficult to draw conclusions about the characteristics of a Minoan pantheon. Iconography is similarly ambiguous. Indeed, it is very challenging to identify images of either rulers or deities in Bronze Age Aegean art more broadly (Davis 1995; Koehl 1995; Blakolmer 2019), though some strong possibilities do exist in the Neopalatial period on Crete (ex. Driessen 2015, 36). These candidates reveal some general iconographic patterns that seem to identify important people within scenes, including seated women, often enthroned on elevated platforms, and floating figures seemingly descending from the sky. Seated females, who look out over the scene and are sometimes approached by other human figures not elevated on platforms, perhaps represent rulers rather than deities, but iconographic similarities between such scenes suggest a supernatural identity. The enthroned, for example, is often accompanied by animals, real or supernatural. These representations, however, have yet to be found amongst peak sanctuary material assemblages; instead, the anthropomorphic figurines found at Petsofas and other peak sanctuaries have no distinguishing divine characteristics, and are therefore more often interpreted as representations of worshippers dedicated at the sanctuary by human pilgrims, rather than those of the supernatural beings for whom they were offered.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The earliest peak sanctuary ritual seems to have emerged out of local religious traditions which became gained formality throughout the Protopalatial Period. By the Neopalatial period, however, the network of peak sanctuary sites and their ritual activities became far more centralized, presumably falling under the control of Minoan ruling powers located at palatial centres across Crete.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Nothing about the material culture found at the Bronze Age peak sanctuary of Petsofas suggests that it specifically commemorated the birthplace of a supernatural being, though it is interesting to note that a sanctuary to Diktaian Zeus was established in the settlement of Roussolakkos, at the foot of Petofas, in the Geometric period and continued in use into the Roman period (8th century BCE to 4th century CE). According to Greek myth, it was here in Dikte that Zeus was born and subsequently hidden from his father, Kronos. Nevertheless, there is no direct evidence

to suggest that peak sanctuary cult as a Bronze Age phenomenon was connected to these later mythological traditions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and

Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsopas

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the lack of historical documents in the Bronze Age and the challenge of identifying a religious hierarchy or Minoan pantheon, it is unknown if a supreme high god existed in Bronze Age Cretan traditions, or if it was worshipped at any particular site.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about the spiritual beliefs and ideologies of the inhabitants of prehistoric Crete.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about the spiritual beliefs and ideologies of the inhabitants of prehistoric Crete.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Very little is known about the spiritual beliefs and ideologies of the inhabitants of prehistoric Crete.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the anthropomorphic terracotta figurines found at Petsopas are more often interpreted as representations of the worshippers dedicated at the sanctuary to a deity or deities, it has been suggested that they may instead represent deities themselves. A specific cult statue, however, is not recognizable amongst the assemblage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsopas

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although animal sacrifices are known to have been conducted in Bronze Age Crete, it is not known if they were ever conducted at peak sanctuaries.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, as ceramic vessels are commonly found at peak sanctuaries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Other

– Other [specify]: In addition to pottery and ceramic figurines (anthropomorphic and zoomorphic), miniature ceramic vessels, "votive limbs," and stone libation tables have also been found at Petsofas.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Scholars sometimes refer to peak sanctuary worshippers as "pilgrims" and their journeys up the mountains to the sanctuaries as "pilgrimages," but these terms are used in a regional sense and do not necessarily refer to long-range travel for the purpose of worship. In fact, John Myres noted that the clay used to create the terracotta figurines found at Petsofas appeared to be local, coming from the "debris of the late clayey limestones of the Palaikastro valley" (1902-3, 360). This observation corroborates Celine Murphy's recent finding that terracotta materials from Cretan peak sanctuaries reflect local provenances, suggesting the local manufacture of these objects (Murphy 2019).

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not definitively known whether or not divination was practiced at Petsofas or other peak sanctuaries due to the lack of written records and material evidence for this practice. This does not, however mean that it was never conducted at these sites.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The best evidence for healing practices at Petsofas and other peak sanctuaries is the presence of terracotta "votive limbs" and other body parts alongside the anthropomorphic and zoomorphic figurines found deposited at these sites. The assemblage from Petsofas remains the best known collection of such votives (Myres 1902-3, plate xii), and include representations of terracotta arms, legs, heads, torsos with breasts or genitalia, and pregnant female bodies, some of which are pierced. Christine Morris and Alan Peatfield (2014, 54-63) suggest that this Petsofas material fits into a

broader healing dimension of peak sanctuary ritual seen in the "anatomical offerings" found at Juktas, Atsipadhes, Traostalos, and Prinias. Conclusive evidence, however, is still unknown, and speculation about a healing aspect of Minoan religion rests on interpretations of material culture.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

Notes: The material evidence points to the practice of small-scale rituals at Petsofas, including the dedication of offerings and libations, and possibly practices of feasting, drinking, and offering of sacrifices.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Field doesn't know.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Field doesn't know.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: Presumably no, as there is no evidence for such resource control at Petsofas; however, if peak sanctuaries were centralized under the control of Minoan palatial elites in the Neopalatial period, it is possible that the sanctuaries played some role in land or resource control across the island.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: While it is possible that services such as healing or feeding the community took place at Petsofas and other peak sanctuaries, the material remains do not explicitly suggest that such activities took place at these sites, and written records are not available to provide detailed accounts. Furthermore, the high-elevation location of such sites would not have made peak sanctuaries convenient locations for community members to seek necessary services. Although Petsofas is more accessible than many other peak sanctuaries, it still involves considerable effort to reach and had a much more accessible settlement nestled at its base.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Petsofas

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Bogdan Rutkowski. *Petsophas: A Cretan Peak Sanctuary*. Warsaw: Art and Archaeology. isbn: 8322106157 9788322106150.

Reference: R. Bosanquet C., R. Dawkins M., Marcus Tod Niebuhr, W. Duckworth L.H., John Myres. *Excavations at Palaikastro II: The Sanctuary-Site of Petsofa*.